

A fully resolved SPH-DEM method for heterogeneous suspensions with arbitrary particle shape

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ABSTRACT

The study on fluid-solid interaction in heterogeneous suspensions is essential for theoretical research and engineering practice. In this paper, a three-dimensional fully resolved SPH-DEM method is presented to model suspensions with non-Newtonian fluids and solid particles of arbitrary shape. The fluid phase is modelled using SPH with a regularized Bingham model, whereas aggregates with irregular shapes is modelled using a DEM method based on surface mesh representation. A simple unified hybrid contact method is proposed to model the SPH-boundary, SPH-DEM, DEM-DEM, and DEM-boundary interactions in a generalized fashion. Furthermore, GPU parallelization is employed to increase the numerical efficiency. The coupling method is validated using numerical examples including: (1) water-entry of a sphere, (2) Poiseuille flow of a Bingham material, (3) collapse of columns of irregular particles, and (4) gravity-driven heterogeneous flows with irregular particle shape. The simulation results indicate that the presented method is suitable for heterogeneous flows with irregular solid particles.

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1. Introduction

Free-surface flows of heterogeneous suspensions are widely present in nature and engineering applications. For instance, landslides and debris flows consisting of water, soil, and rocks are destructive natural hazards, causing huge losses of property and human life [1,2]. In civil engineering, fresh concretes composed of cement paste and aggregates are one of the most important construction materials [3,4]. Moreover, applications involving heterogeneous suspensions can also be found in oil industry, mineral processing, milling, bed fluidization, and chemical reactors, among others [5].

Characterizing and modelling of heterogeneous suspensions is a challenging task mainly due to the complexity of the solid phase and the fluid-solid interaction. Solids in suspensions usually have varying solid volume fractions, extremely wide ranges of grain size, and arbitrarily irregular grain shapes [2,3,6,7]. In many cases, suspensions are considered as single-phase homogeneous materials or multiphase solid-water mixtures [8,9]. This treatment has the advantage of simplicity in constitutive characterizing and numerical modelling. For example, to capture rheological behaviour of heterogeneous suspensions, various constitutive models such as viscoplastic models [10–16], hypoplastic models [17,18], and the $\mu(I)$ model [19,20] were employed. Furthermore, various numerical methods were also developed to simulate heterogeneous suspensions in the continuum framework [21–24].

However, many distinct phenomena such as particle segregation [25], arching [26], and dilatancy [27] are closely related to grain size distribution and complex irregular shape, which cannot be sufficiently considered using continuum approaches.

Continuum-discrete approaches are rational choice for modelling heterogeneous suspensions, where fluids or mixtures of fluids and fine solid particles can be modelled as continuum with constitutive models, whereas large solid particles can be considered using discrete approaches. The discrete element method (DEM) is an ideal tool for granular system, and are coupled with computational fluid dynamics (CFD) to model heterogeneous suspensions [28–32]. Based on how to model interactions between particles and fluids, existing coupled CFD-DEM approaches can be mainly categorized into two groups: the unresolved and resolved approaches [33], which are also termed as the averaged volume method (AVM) and the immersed family methods (IMF) [34]. In the unresolved approaches, interaction forces are based on empirical formulas depending on relative velocities and local solid volume fractions. Many CFD methods including finite volume method (FVM) [29,30], finite element method (FEM) [35], particle FEM (PFEM) [36], and various meshless methods [32,37], are coupled with DEM in the unresolved way to solve fluid-particle coupling problems. Because large grid size in CFD can be used, unresolved approaches are more computationally efficient compared to resolved approaches [33]. In simulations using the unresolved approaches, spherical DEM particles are usually employed to model the solid phase. Nevertheless, to better consider the influence of particle shape, methods using non-spherical particles were also developed for industrial and engineering applications [38–40].

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Alternatively, in the resolved CFD-DEM coupling approaches, the DEM particles serves as the boundaries for the fluid phase. The hydrodynamic forces are calculated based on the fluid-solid interaction along the particle surface [34]. As the fluid flow are modelled considering the realistic particle shape and spacing, the resolved approaches are regarded to be more accurate than the unresolved approaches [41]. Because the DEM particles are treated as moving boundaries, grid-based fluid solvers need special numerical techniques to achieve the fluid-solid coupling. Popular techniques are the immersed boundary methods [42,43], which employ two sets of independent meshes, and the moving mesh methods [28,44], which use one set of moving mesh. Interested readers can refer to the review paper of Zhong et al. [34] to find more information on the resolved coupling between grid-based methods and DEM.

In the last two decades, meshless Lagrangian particle-based methods, e.g. smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) [45] and moving particle semi-implicit method (MPS) [46] were developed to model free-surface flows. These methods are convenient to model transient problems with free-surfaces and moving interfaces. They are promising candidate for the fluid solver in a coupled CFD-DEM framework, because they do not need additional numerical techniques to track the complex fluid-particle interfaces. Recently, Robb et al. [47] and Canelas et al. [48] developed SPH-DEM models for free-surface flows containing floating objects. Trujillo-Vela et al. [49] proposed a SPH-DEM scheme for the simulation of debris flows with boulders. Nevertheless, heterogeneous flows with non-Newtonian fluids and arbitrarily irregular particles have not been investigated with SPH.

In this work, we aim to develop a general three-dimensional numerical framework for heterogeneous suspensions with non-Newtonian fluids and arbitrarily irregular particles. The fluid and solid phases are modelled using SPH and a recently developed surface mesh represented DEM (SMR-DEM) [50], respectively. The regularized Bingham model is incorporated into SPH to model interstitial free-surface non-Newtonian flows. In SMR-DEM, solid particles of arbitrary shapes are discretized using contact nodes obtained through surface mesh. A unified hybrid contact scheme, based on our previous hybrid contact model [50,51], is developed for convenient and efficient computation of DEM particle-particle contact, SPH-DEM interaction, and SPH boundary treatment. Furthermore, based on graphic processing units (GPUs), massive parallelization of the proposed coupling framework are developed to achieve high efficiency.

The remaining part of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly introduces the SPH method and the constitutive model for non-Newtonian fluids. Section 3 presents the framework of SMR-DEM for particles of arbitrarily irregular shape. The unified hybrid contact scheme for SPH-DEM coupling and SPH boundary treatment is presented in Section 4. The numerical implementation and GPU parallelization are introduced in Section 5. Section 6 and 7 present validation cases and conclusions, respectively.

2. SPH for non-Newtonian free-surface flows

2.1. Governing equations and material model

The motion of non-Newtonian free-surface flows is governed by mass and momentum conservation equations. Their Lagrangian forms are given as follows [52].

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho\nabla\cdot\mathbf{v} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} = \frac{1}{\rho}\nabla\cdot\boldsymbol{\sigma} + \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{f}^{\text{ext}} \quad (2)$$

where $D(\cdot)/Dt$ represents the material derivative; ρ and \mathbf{v} are the fluid density and velocity, respectively; \mathbf{g} is the acceleration due to gravity.

\mathbf{f}^{ext} represents the external forces from DEM particles and rigid boundaries. $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor which can be decomposed into pressure p and shear stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\tau}$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = -p\mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the 3×3 identity matrix.

In this work, the pressure is computed directly from density variation based on the assumption that the fluid is weakly-compressible. According to the equation of state in [45], the pressure is calculated by

$$p = \frac{c_0^2\rho_0}{\gamma} \left[\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^\gamma - 1 \right] \quad (4)$$

where c_0 is the speed of sound, ρ_0 is the reference density, γ is a constant usually taken as 7. In SPH simulations, c_0 is not the physical speed of sound of the fluid, but a parameter used to control the compressibility [45]. Usually, c_0 is selected to be 10 times larger than the expected maximum velocity in the flow. This is to ensure that the Mach number of the flow is less than 0.1 and the compressibility of the fluid is less than 1% [45,53].

The non-Newtonian fluid phase in heterogeneous suspensions is modelled using the Bingham model, which specify that materials start to flow like a Newtonian fluid only when the stress exceeds a threshold, which is termed as yield stress. In three dimensions, the shear stress tensor in Bingham fluids is calculated as

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = 2 \left(\mu_0 + \frac{\tau_0}{|\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}|} \right) \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \quad (5)$$

where μ_0 and τ_0 represent the plastic viscosity and yield stress, respectively. $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$ is the strain rate tensor defined as

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} = \frac{1}{2} (\nabla\mathbf{v} + (\nabla\mathbf{v})^T) \quad (6)$$

and $|\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}|$ is the equivalent strain rate calculated as $|\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}| = \sqrt{2\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}:\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}}$. It is found that Eq. (5) becomes singular when the strain rate is zero in the static state. To remove this singularity, the regularized Bingham model proposed by Papanastasiou [54] is employed

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = 2 \left(\mu_0 + \frac{\tau_0}{|\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}|} (1 - e^{-m|\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}|}) \right) \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \quad (7)$$

where m is a regularization parameter which determines how close the regularized model approximates the original Bingham model. It can be found that the regularized model is close to the original one when m is large enough [55]. Theoretically, a very large m should be used in the simulation. However, a very large m leads to extremely large viscosities ($\mu_0 + m\tau_0$) in the areas with shear rate close to zero. Because SPH employs explicit time integration methods to solve the governing equations, very large viscosities may impose strict restrictions on the time step size and lead to decreased efficiency. In practice, m is chosen to be as small as possible, but large enough to reproduce correct flow physics. In previous SPH modelling of free-surface non-Newtonian flows, it is found that when m is between 100 and 1000, the numerical results are almost identical [14]. Consequently, $m = 1000$ is used in this study.

2.2. SPH formulations

In SPH, the material domain is partitioned into particles carrying field variables such as mass, density, pressure, and velocity and moving with the material [56–58]. As a meshless method, the governing equations are solved by tracking the motions of particles and the changes of carried field variables. In SPH, a generic function $f(\mathbf{x})$ and its gradient

$\nabla f(\mathbf{x})$ can be approximated by the following integrals over the supported domain Ω [59–61].

$$\langle f(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \int_{\Omega} f(\mathbf{x}') W(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', h) d\mathbf{x}' \quad (8)$$

$$\langle \nabla f(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = \int_{\Omega} f(\mathbf{x}') \nabla W(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', h) d\mathbf{x}' \quad (9)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ represents the kernel approximation, \mathbf{x} is the spatial coordinates, $W(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', h)$ denotes the kernel function which depends on the distance $\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'\|$ and the smoothing length h . In this study, the Wendland C2 kernel [62] is used

$$W(q, h) = \alpha_d \left(1 - \frac{q}{2}\right)^4 (2q + 1) \quad 0 \leq q \leq 2 \quad (10)$$

where $q = \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'\|/h$ is the normalized distance, α_d is a normalization factor which is $7/(4\pi h^2)$ in 2D and $21/(16\pi h^3)$ in 3D [63]. It was reported that the Wendland kernel increases the stability of SPH computations [64] and provides more accurate results [65].

With SPH particles, the continuous functions of $\langle f(\mathbf{x}) \rangle$ and its derivative $\langle \nabla f(\mathbf{x}) \rangle$ at each SPH particle can be approximated as the summation of contributions from all particles in the support domain [59–61]:

$$f(\mathbf{x}_i) = \sum_j f(\mathbf{x}_j) W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h) \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} \quad (11)$$

$$\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_i) = \sum_j f(\mathbf{x}_j) \nabla_i W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h) \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} \quad (12)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is omitted for convenience. \mathbf{x}_i represents the central particle where the approximation is applied, and \mathbf{x}_j denotes the particles within the supported domain of particle \mathbf{x}_i . m and ρ represent the particle mass and density, respectively. For the sake of simplicity, hereafter $W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h)$ and $\nabla_i W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h)$ will be replaced by W_{ij} and $\nabla_i W_{ij}$, respectively.

Applying Eq. (12) to Eq. (1), the SPH discretized form of continuity equation can be written as

$$\frac{D\rho_i}{Dt} = \sum_j m_j (\mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} + \delta h c_0 \sum_j \frac{2m_j}{\rho_j} (\rho_i - \rho_j) \frac{\mathbf{r}_{ij}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{ij}\|^2 + 0.01h^2} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{r}_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j$ is the vector from \mathbf{x}_j to \mathbf{x}_i . It is well-known that the classical weakly-compressible SPH [45] suffers from pressure fluctuations [53,66]. The second term on the right hand side of the above equation is an additional density diffusion term called δ -SPH [66], which is employed to improve pressure results. The constant δ is used to control the intensity of the density diffusion. A too small δ is not enough to give smooth pressure results, whereas a too large δ induces excessive damping. From theoretical analysis [66] and a wide range of numerical tests [14,66–71], it is found that $\delta = 0.1$ is an appropriate choice in SPH simulations for both Newtonian and non-Newtonian flows.

The discretized momentum conservation equation is written as

$$\frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt} = \sum_j m_j \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_j}{\rho_j^2} + \frac{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i}{\rho_i^2} - \Pi_{ij} \mathbf{I} \right) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} + \mathbf{g}_i + \mathbf{f}_i^{\text{ext}} \quad (14)$$

where the first term on the right hand side represents the contribution of stress gradient. $\Pi_{ij} = \Pi_{ij}^{\text{vis}} + \Pi_{ij}^{\text{p}}$ is the stabilization term including the corrections by artificial viscosity Π_{ij}^{vis} and artificial pressure Π_{ij}^{p} . The artificial viscosity is used to prevent numerical instability and unphysical particle penetration, whereas the artificial pressure is employed to alleviate the tensile instability. The Monaghan types of artificial viscosity and artificial pressure are employed in this paper, which are presented in detail in [45,72].

3. SMR-DEM for particles of arbitrary shape

Originally proposed by Cundall and Strack [73], DEM is extensively applied to simulations of granular assemblies. In DEM, the movements of solid particles including translations and rotations are tracked by solving Newton's equations of motion

$$M_k \frac{d\mathbf{v}_k}{dt} = \mathbf{F}_k^s + \mathbf{F}_k^f + M_k \mathbf{g} \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{J}_k \frac{d\boldsymbol{\Omega}_k}{dt} = \mathbf{T}_k^s + \mathbf{T}_k^f - \boldsymbol{\Omega}_k \times \mathbf{J}_k \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega}_k \quad (16)$$

where M_k and \mathbf{J}_k represent the mass and moment of inertial matrix of particle k . \mathbf{v}_k and $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_k$ are the translational and angular velocities, respectively. \mathbf{F}_k and \mathbf{T}_k denote the total force and torque acting on the k -th particle, and the superscripts s and f represent the force or torque exerted by the solid and fluid phases, respectively. The moment of inertia matrix \mathbf{J} , which is initially calculated and stored in the body-fixed coordinates system, needs to be rotated to the current angular position of particle in the simulation [27].

In most DEM simulations, the solid phase is modelled as spherical particles, which allow fast and straightforward contact detection and force computation. On the other hand, the need of representing accurate particle shape in many applications also motivates researches on DEM modelling of non-spherical particles. To date, many non-spherical DEM techniques have been developed, including polygon/polyhedron [74–77], multi-spheres [78,79], superquadrics [80,81], discrete function representation (DFR-DEM) [82,83], level-set DEM (LS-DEM) [84,85], and Gilbert-Johnson-Keerthi algorithm-based DEM (GJK-DEM) [27,86], among others. Despite these great progresses, the modelling of arbitrarily shaped particles still remains challenging. Particularly, considering that fully resolved SPH-DEM coupling needs to handle additional interactions between SPH and DEM particles, a convenient and efficient technique for shape representation and contact detection of complex particle shape is required. In this work, a surface mesh represented discrete element method (SMR-DEM) is employed for three-dimensional modelling of granular assemblies of arbitrary shape. Here we only briefly introduce SMR-DEM, more details can be found in [50].

Fig. 1 shows the particle representation and contact detection in SMR-DEM. Particles are represented by contact nodes, which can be obtained as vertices of triangular surface meshes. The shape representation using surface mesh has mainly two benefits. First, particles of arbitrarily irregular shape can be represented without difficulty. Second, particle shape data obtained from X-ray CT, scanning electron microscope (SEM), the Structure-in-motion technique, or computer-aided design (CAD), are usually in the form of triangular surface mesh. In SMR-DEM, owing to the direct employment of surface mesh, additional pre-processing techniques such as filling algorithms in the multi-spheres methods [87–89], or function description in DFR-DEM [83], LS-DEM [84] and GJK-DEM [27] are not needed.

The contact detection in computational mechanics can be generally grouped into three categories, i.e. node-to-node (NTN), node-to-segment (NTS), and segment-to-segment (STS). The node-to-node methods are the simplest. It assumes that if the distance between two nodes are smaller than a criterion then they are in contact, and the contact force is in the line connecting the two nodes. The sphere-to-sphere contact in DEM [73] and the pinball contact in SPH [90] are typical NTN methods. The contact force in NTN methods is less accurate if the contact bodies are not spheres or disks [51]. The NTS methods discretize contact surfaces using segments (2D) or faces (3D), and the computation is based on the contact relationship between nodes (vertices) and faces [91,92]. Methods based on NTS give more correct contact normals, and are popular in DEM methods for non-spherical particles [27,84]. Moreover, the STS methods are based on segment-to-segment contact, which have high accuracy and are mainly employed in contact

Fig. 1. Illustration of the particle representation and contact detection [50] in SMR-DEM.

mechanics [93,94] and domain decomposition [95,96]. The application of STS methods in DEM has not yet been reported, probably due to their high computational cost and complex implementation.

In this study, a hybrid contact detection method is employed, which combines the convenience of node-to-node (NTN) method and the accuracy of node-to-segment (NTS) method. The contact detection is only based on contact nodes carrying surface unit normals, which are computed by averaging the unit normals of associated triangles [50]. Note that the surface mesh is only used to determine the locations of contact nodes and unit normals, they are not used in the contact detection like in the NTS methods. As illustrated in Fig. 1(b), two particles in potential contact are termed as master and slave particles according to their index. For each contact node \mathbf{x}_s on the slave surface, we search for the nearest master contact node \mathbf{x}_m . The distance d between the node pair is defined as

$$d = (\mathbf{x}_s - \mathbf{x}_m) \cdot \mathbf{n}_c \quad (17)$$

where \mathbf{n}_c is the contact unit normal, which depends on the unit normals at the master and slave contact nodes. The details on the determination of \mathbf{n}_c can be found in [50]. The contact is activated when $d < 0$, and the overlap $d_p = -d$ is used to calculate the contact forces between the two contact nodes. It can be found that in the hybrid contact model, the contact computation is based on the actual local unit normal of the contact surfaces. Compared with the NTN method, the employed contact unit normal is more accurate than the unit vector connecting the two contact nodes [51]. On the other hand, it avoids the complicated three-dimensional projection determination and distance computation in the NTS method [97].

The time-driven soft-sphere approach is employed in SMR-DEM to compute contact forces. The normal component of the contact force acting on the slave contact node is calculated using a spring-dashpot contact model

$$\mathbf{f}_s^n = (k_n d_p + \eta \Delta v_n) \mathbf{n}_c \quad (18)$$

where Δv_n is the normal component of the relative velocity between the contact nodes \mathbf{x}_m and \mathbf{x}_s , k_n is the normal contact stiffness, and η is the contact damping parameter which can be calculated based on the restitution [98].

$$\eta = -2 \ln e \sqrt{\frac{k_n M^*}{\ln^2 e + \pi^2}} \quad (19)$$

where e is the restitution coefficient, $M^* = M_s M_m / (M_s + M_m)$ is the reduced mass of the contact particles. For the collision between particles and rigid walls, it has $M^* = M_s$. The tangential friction force is calculated with an upper limit given by the Coulomb law of friction

$$\mathbf{f}_s^t = \begin{cases} \mu \|\mathbf{f}_s^n\| \frac{\mathbf{v}_t}{\|\mathbf{v}_t\|} & \|\mathbf{f}_s^t\| \geq \mu \|\mathbf{f}_s^n\| \\ k_t \Delta \mathbf{d}_t & \|\mathbf{f}_s^t\| < \mu \|\mathbf{f}_s^n\| \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where k_t is the tangential contact stiffness, μ is the frictional coefficient between the two particles in contact. \mathbf{v}_t and $\Delta \mathbf{d}_t$ are the relative velocity and incremental relative displacement in the tangential direction, respectively. They can be computed as follows

$$\mathbf{v}_t = (\mathbf{v}_m - \mathbf{v}_s) - [\mathbf{n}_c \cdot (\mathbf{v}_m - \mathbf{v}_s)] \mathbf{n}_c \quad (21)$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{d}_t = \mathbf{v}_t \Delta t \quad (22)$$

Finally, the contact force acting on the slave contact node is obtained as

$$\mathbf{f}_s = \mathbf{f}_s^n + \mathbf{f}_s^t \quad (23)$$

According to the Newton's third law, the master contact node takes an equal and opposite reaction from the slave contact node. The total contact force and contact moment acting on each DEM particle are obtained by summing up the contributions from all the contact nodes as following

$$\mathbf{F}_k^s = \sum_i^{N_k} \mathbf{f}_{si} \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{T}_k^s = \sum_i^{N_k} \mathbf{r}_i \times \mathbf{f}_{si} \quad (25)$$

where \mathbf{f}_{si} is the contact force at contact node i calculated by Eq. (23), $\mathbf{r}_i = \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{X}_k$ is the relative position vector between the contact node \mathbf{x}_i and the center of mass \mathbf{X}_k . N_k is the total number of contact nodes of the k -th particle.

Finally, the position of the centroid \mathbf{X}_k and the accumulated rotated angle Θ_k are updated by integrating the translation velocity \mathbf{V}_k and the angular velocity $\mathbf{\Omega}_k$. Consequently, the position \mathbf{x}_i and velocity \mathbf{v}_i of the contact nodes can be updated using the position of centroid, rotated angle, and particle translational and angular velocities as follows

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{R}_k \cdot (\mathbf{x}_{i0} - \mathbf{X}_{k0}) \quad (26)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_i = \mathbf{V}_k + \mathbf{\Omega}_k \times (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{X}_k) \quad (27)$$

where \mathbf{R}_k is the rotation matrix, which is a function of the vector of accumulated rotated angle Θ_k and is derived from quaternions. \mathbf{x}_{i0} and \mathbf{X}_{k0} are the initial positions of \mathbf{x}_i and the centroid of the k -th DEM particle, respectively.

4. Resolved coupling between SPH and SMR-DEM

4.1. Coupling framework

In the resolved coupling between SPH and DEM, the surfaces of DEM particles are treated as rigid moving boundaries for the SPH fluid phase. The interaction forces are computed by integrating stresses on the DEM particle surfaces. In this work, we focus on heterogeneous suspensions with particles of arbitrary shape; therefore, a method capable of computing interactions along arbitrarily complex moving interfaces should be developed.

In previous studies, approaches for resolved SPH-DEM coupling can be mainly grouped into two categories. In the first one, floating solid objects are discretized as SPH boundary particles using the same numerical resolution as that in the fluid phase. The interaction between fluid and floating objects are handled in the same way as that for boundary treatment, using methods such as dynamic boundary condition [48], extrapolated pressure method [47], and ghost particle method [99]. The advantage of these boundary treatment-based methods is that the viscous effect is automatically included in the SPH momentum equation, so additional considerations of viscous forces are not required. Moreover, because multiple layers of boundary particles are employed, the truncated SPH support domains are completed, resulting in higher accuracy in the fluid computation. On the other hand, multiple layers of boundary particles lead to increased computational cost, and in some cases it is also difficult to place several layers of particles in small or thin objects. Furthermore, in practice, the interaction forces obtained from the SPH momentum equation cannot completely prevent particle penetration.

The other category of SPH-DEM interaction is based on contact mechanics, which consider normal and tangential contact forces separately. The normal contact force is usually computed using DEM-like penalty methods [49,51,100,101]. In the tangential direction, the frictional contact and the viscous effect can be considered for solid [51] and fluid [49], respectively. The contact-based approaches do not need additional boundary particles, but require explicit contact detection. The SPH particle penetration can also be completely avoided. The contact-based approaches does not include the treatment of boundary deficiency; thus, the accuracy of the fluid computation might be lower.

In this work, the interaction between non-Newtonian fluids and solid particles is calculated using a unified hybrid contact method. The hybrid contact model employed in SMR-DEM and soil-structure interaction [51] is extended to consider fluid-solid interaction. Fig. 2 shows the implicit surface discretization and the contact detection for the SPH-DEM coupling. The contact is based on the same surface mesh representation employed in DEM computations. As shown in Fig. 2, DEM particles are discretized with contact nodes carrying unit normals. For a fluid particle \mathbf{x}_f , the nearest contact node \mathbf{x}_s is first identified. Then the distance between the fluid particle \mathbf{x}_f and the DEM particle containing the contact node \mathbf{x}_s is defined as

$$d = (\mathbf{x}_s - \mathbf{x}_f) \cdot \mathbf{n}_s \quad (28)$$

Fig. 2. The two-dimensional schematic diagram of contact detection in SPH-DEM.

where \mathbf{n}_s is the unit normal of the contact node. The subscripts s and f denote the contact node and the fluid particle, respectively. The contact is activated when

$$d < \frac{\Delta x}{2} \quad (29)$$

where Δx is the initial SPH particle spacing. The contact criterion is the present form because a SPH particle represents a portion of volume and is generally considered having a size of Δx . A similar criterion is employed in [100] to model soil-structure interactions. If a contact is detected, the penetration d_p is determined as $d_p = \Delta x/2 - d$. It can be seen that the process of contact detection in the coupled SPH-DEM is almost the same as that in SMR-DEM. It is also found that with the unified hybrid contact method, SPH particles are in contact with the implicit DEM particle surface shown in Fig. 2. The implicit surface is slightly different from the polygonal/polyhedral surface defined by the surface mesh, although the difference becomes smaller when more contact nodes are used to represent the DEM particle.

4.2. Normal coupling force

Once a SPH-DEM contact pair is determined to be active, the normal force exerted on the fluid particle is computed based on the assumption of partial penetration defined as

$$\mathbf{f}_f^n = k_f^n d_p \mathbf{n}_s \quad (30)$$

where

k_f^n is the normal stiffness coefficient, which is computed as $k_f^n = \zeta m_f / \Delta t^2$ with $\zeta = 0.1$ being a factor to weaken the contact stiffness [100]. m_f is the mass of the fluid particle, and Δt is the computational time step. This direct enforcement of penalty force guarantees the impenetrability between the SPH and DEM particles, hence the stability of computations.

4.3. Tangential coupling force

In SPH, the viscous tangential force is computed based on the Laplacian term using the integral approximation [102]. However, due to the incomplete support domain truncated by the DEM particle (Fig. 3a), there should be additional treatments for the truncated part. Traditionally, SPH employs the boundary particle method (Fig. 3b) or the boundary integration method (Fig. 3c) to handle the boundary deficiency [47,48,103,104]. However, both the two methods have difficulties in a SPH-DEM coupling method aiming to model a large amount of DEM particles of complex irregular shape. In this study, a simpler method is developed to compute the tangential viscous force, using only a single pair of SPH particle and DEM contact node.

The concept of the viscous force computation is similar to that in [49,101]. The viscous tangential force is considered when the distance between a SPH particle and its nearest contact node is less than $2h$. Following the SPH discretization of the viscous Laplacian term in [102], an extra viscous term is applied to the pair of SPH particle and contact node.

$$\mathbf{f}_f^t = m_f \left\langle \frac{1}{\rho} (\nabla \mu \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} \right\rangle_f = m_f^2 \frac{2\mu_{app}}{\rho_f^2} \frac{\mathbf{r}_{fs} \cdot \tilde{\nabla}_f W_{fs}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{fs}\|^2 + 0.01h^2} \mathbf{v}_{fs}^t \quad (31)$$

where $\tilde{\nabla}_f W_{fs}$ is a renormalized kernel gradient, whose definition will be detailed later. $\mathbf{r}_{fs} = \mathbf{x}_f - \mathbf{x}_s$ is the vector from the contact node \mathbf{x}_s to the SPH particle \mathbf{x}_f . μ_{app} is the apparent viscosity of the non-Newton fluid, which is calculated using the regularized Bingham model

$$\mu_{app} = \mu_0 + \frac{\tau_0}{|\dot{\gamma}|} (1 - e^{-m|\dot{\gamma}|}) \quad (32)$$

Fig. 3. The boundary deficiency in SPH and various methods to couple SPH and DEM.

\mathbf{v}_{fs}^t in Eq. (31) represents the relative velocity between the SPH particle and the contact node in the tangential direction, which can be calculated as

$$\mathbf{v}_{fs}^t = (\mathbf{v}_f - \mathbf{v}_s) - [\mathbf{n}_s \cdot (\mathbf{v}_f - \mathbf{v}_s)] \mathbf{n}_s \quad (33)$$

where \mathbf{v}_f denotes the velocity of the SPH particle, and \mathbf{v}_s is the velocity of the contact node calculated by Eq. (27).

It can be seen that the contribution of the truncated support domain to the viscous force is computed based on a single contact node. This leads to huge errors if the original kernel gradient $\nabla_f W_{fs}$ is employed. To account for the truncated part, a renormalized kernel gradient is employed. First, following Nassauer et al. [101] and Trujillo-Vela et al. [49], the original kernel gradient $\nabla_f W_{fs}$ is replaced by the gradient of the corresponding one-dimensional kernel function $\nabla_f W_{fs}^1$, where the superscript 1 indicates that the kernel function is one-dimensional. The one-dimensional Wendland kernel function writes [62].

$$W^1(q, h) = \frac{5}{8h} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2}q\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}q^3\right) \quad 0 \leq q \leq 2 \quad (34)$$

The definitions of q and h are the same as those in Eq. (10). If we assume that in the 1D condition there are only the contact node s and the fluid particle f , following the kernel gradient correction in Chen et al. [105], a correction coefficient L_f can be obtained as

$$L_f = \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} (\mathbf{x}_s - \mathbf{x}_f) \nabla_f W_{fs}^1 \frac{m_s}{\rho_s} \quad (35)$$

where m_s and ρ_s are the virtual mass and density of the contact node, which are taken the same as those of the fluid particle f . Using the correction coefficient, the renormalized kernel gradient is defined as

$$\tilde{\nabla}_f W_{fs} = \frac{\xi}{\Delta x^2} \tilde{\nabla}_f W_{fs}^1 = \frac{\xi}{\Delta x^2} \frac{\nabla_f W_{fs}^1}{L_f} \quad (36)$$

where the term Δx^2 is used to correct the 1D kernel gradient for 3D simulations. The coefficient ξ is the fraction of the truncated part of the support domain. It is used to correct the computed viscous forces, because the forces from other SPH fluid particles are already considered. ξ can be estimated using the following equation

$$\xi = \frac{1}{2} - \int_0^{|\mathbf{x}_s - \mathbf{x}_f|} x \nabla W^1(x) dx \approx \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\Delta x/2} x \nabla W^1(x) dx \quad (37)$$

Note that ξ is a constant depending on the initial particle spacing Δx and the kernel type. It can be computed at the beginning of the simulation. With the renormalized kernel gradient $\tilde{\nabla}_f W_{fs}$, the viscous force on the boundary can be approximated using Eq. (31) with a single pair of SPH particle and contact node. A more detailed derivation of the renormalized kernel gradient can be found in Appendix A.

Consequently, the total force acting on the fluid particle from a DEM solid particle is obtained as

$$\mathbf{f}_f = \mathbf{f}_f^n + \mathbf{f}_f^f \quad (38)$$

The interaction forces between a SPH particle and its surrounding DEM particles are then summed up as \mathbf{f}^{ext} in Eq. (2). According to Newton's third law, the contact node takes an equal and opposite reaction from the SPH particles defined as $\mathbf{f}_s = -\mathbf{f}_f$. By adding the reaction force \mathbf{f}_s into Eq. (24) and Eq. (25), the total force \mathbf{F}_k^f and torque \mathbf{T}_k^f from the fluid phase to the solid objects are obtained. Finally, the total forces are added to the momentum eqs. (15) and (16) to compute the translational and rotational accelerations, which are then used to update the velocity of SPH particles and DEM objects.

In this study, SPH solid boundaries, which are either fixed or moved with prescribed velocities, are also treated as DEM object represented by surface contact nodes. With the surface mesh representation, solid boundaries of arbitrary complex geometry can be modelled straightforwardly. In the resolved SPH-DEM coupled method, the SPH-boundary,

SPH-DEM, DEM-DEM, and DEM-boundary interactions are all handled using the presented unified hybrid contact method.

5. GPU acceleration and implementation

In three-dimensional fully resolved SPH-DEM coupled modelling, the computational cost is high because a large number of SPH particles and contact nodes are needed to reproduce the complex physical process and give accurate numerical results. Fortunately, both SPH and SMR-DEM are suitable for parallel computing. Moreover, the unified hybrid contact method avoids complex geometry computations and can be performed parallelly. The computations at SPH particles and DEM contact nodes are independent. Therefore, the computations can be distributed over many threads and performed simultaneously, resulting in significant increase in numerical efficiency. In recent years, hardware acceleration using graphic unit processors (GPUs) becomes increasingly popular in high-performance computing. Parallelization based on GPU was applied in numerical simulations of SPH [106,107], DEM [108,109], and coupled SPH-DEM [5,110] in the literature. In this work, the GPU parallelization based on the Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) is used to improve the numerical efficiency.

The computational tasks for the presented SPH-DEM coupling method mainly consists of the computations of SPH, DEM, and their coupling. For the fluid modelling, SPH computations include three processes: neighbour search, particle interaction, and time integration. The GPU implementation for these processes is the same as that in [71,107,111]. As for SMR-DEM, the most time-consuming process is the contact computation, including finding the potential master-slave contact nodes and calculating the forces. The cell-linked list used for SPH neighbour search [107,112] is again employed for the contact detection in SMR-DEM. Therefore, in the coupled SPH-DEM, two different cell-linked lists are created: one for SPH fluid particles and the other for DEM contact nodes. Once the potential master-slave contact nodes are determined, they are used in contact status checking and subsequent force computing. For the interaction between SPH particles and contact nodes, the same process is performed to find the nearest pair of SPH particle and contact node using the cell-linked lists. After finishing the force computation, the total force and torque on solid particles are obtained by summing up contributions from all its contact nodes. This summation is achieved using the atomic operation provided by CUDA, which ensures that writing to the same memory address by multiple threads can be performed parallelly without memory racing [113].

Various explicit time integration schemes can be used to solve the governing equations discussed in Section 2 and Section 3. In this work, the second-order accurate leap-frog algorithm is adopted because of its low memory requirement and high efficiency. The updating of field variables in SPH simulation has the same form as those in [100,114]. In DEM simulations, the quaternion is used to describe the particle orientation [115,116]. The leap-frog scheme presented in [27,117] is implemented in this work to integrate the governing equations

$$\mathbb{V}(t + \Delta t/2) = \mathbb{V}(t - \Delta t/2) + \mathbb{A}(t)\Delta t \quad (39a)$$

$$\mathbb{X}(t + \Delta t) = \mathbb{X}(t) + \mathbb{V}(t + \Delta t/2)\Delta t \quad (39b)$$

where \mathbb{V} , \mathbb{A} , and \mathbb{X} denote the generic (translational and angular) velocity, acceleration, and position of SPH and DEM particles, respectively. Δt is the time step.

To ensure the stability of the coupled SPH-DEM method, the time step Δt must satisfy:

$$\Delta t = \min(\Delta t_f, \Delta t_{cv}, \Delta t_s) \quad (40a)$$

$$\Delta t_f = 0.1 \min_i \left(\sqrt{h/\|\mathbf{a}_i\|} \right) \quad (40b)$$

Fig. 4. The flowchart of the computation.

$$\Delta t_{cv} = 0.1 \frac{h}{c_f} \quad (40c)$$

$$\Delta t_s = 0.1 \sqrt{m_s/k_n} \quad (40d)$$

where \mathbf{a}_i denotes the acceleration at the fluid particle i . The speed of sound in the fluid is $c_f = \max(c_0, 10\|\mathbf{v}_i\|_{\max})$, where $\|\mathbf{v}_i\|_{\max}$ is the maximum velocity of fluid particles. m_s is the minimum mass of the DEM particles, and k_n is the normal contact stiffness.

The computational process is shown in Fig. 4. At the beginning, the SPH particles and DEM objects are read from input files and stored in the CPU memory. Then all the information are uploaded into the GPU memory. The actual computations are executed by GPU in a massively parallel fashion. At the beginning of each computational step, two cell-linked lists are created for the SPH particles and DEM objects, and a time step is estimated. Then the SPH-SPH, DEM-DEM, and DEM-SPH interactions are computed. The forces and torques on SPH particles and DEM contact nodes are summed up. Then the velocities and positions of SPH particles, DEM objects and contact nodes are updated using the leap-frog method. The information are occasionally downloaded from the GPU memory to the CPU memory for output purpose. All computational intensive operations are performed by GPU, the CPU is only used to control the computational process. The CPU-GPU memory transfer is minimized to increase the efficiency. We also summarize the computations in one step in Algorithm 1. The implementation and GPU parallelization of the proposed SPH-DEM framework are based on the open-source solver LOQUAT [107], which is originally developed for GPU-accelerated SPH simulation.

Algorithm 1: The algorithm for coupled SPH-DEM in one computational step

1. Compute the time step Δt ;
2. Update the neighbor lists for fluid particles and contact nodes;
3. Calculate strain rate tensors for fluid particles and compute Cauchy stress tensors based on the Bingham model;
4. Detect contact states between SPH and DEM particles, and among DEM particles, compute contact forces;
5. Compute the density rate $\dot{\rho}_i$ and acceleration \mathbf{a}_i from internal force, gravity and interaction force with solid particles for fluid particles;
6. Compute the acceleration of translation velocity $\dot{\mathbf{V}}_k$ and angular velocity $\dot{\mathbf{\Omega}}_k$ for DEM particles;
7. Update the velocity, angular velocity, position, and quaternion of DEM particles, update the velocity and position of contact nodes;
8. Update the velocity, position, and density of fluid particles, compute the new pressure of fluid particles based on the equation of state;

6. Validation studies

6.1. Water entry of a sphere

A problem of water entry of a sphere is simulated with the presented SPH-DEM method to check its performance in model fluid-solid interaction. The problem was experimentally investigated by Aristoff et al. [118], and was later modelled using a coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian method (CEL) [119]. The setup of the problem is shown in Fig. 5. A tank has dimensions of $0.2 \times 0.2 \times 0.2$ m and is filled with water. The depth of the water is 0.15 m. Initially, the water is at rest. A sphere of radius 12.7 mm is released from the water surface with an initial velocity of 2.17 m/s. To investigate the influence of sphere density, three spheres with different materials were used in the experiment, whose densities are 860, 1140, and 2300 kg/m³, respectively.

Three numerical simulations following the experimental configuration are carried out using the SPH-DEM coupled method. The sphere is modelled as a rigid object using SMR-DEM. 600 contact nodes are used to represent the sphere. The fluid is modelled using SPH with a initial particle spacing of 1.5 mm, which is close to the average node spacing of the sphere. The material properties of the water are: density $\rho_w = 1000$ kg/m³, dynamic viscosity $\mu_w = 0.001$ Pa·s.

Fig. 6 gives the evolution of water-entry depth, the numerical results are compared with the experimental [118] and CEL [119] results. It is observed that the SPH-DEM method correctly models the evolution of water-entry depth. The larger the sphere density, the faster the sphere travels in the water. The de-acceleration of a sphere with larger density is slower. The results obtained from SPH-DEM and CEL are almost identical, although they both slightly under-predict the entry depth compared with the experimental results. The comparison shows that for this problem the presented SPH-DEM method can achieve an accuracy

Fig. 5. The setup of the water-entry problem.

similar to that of the grid-based method, meaning that the SPH fluid solver and the SPH-DEM coupling method are reliable.

Fig. 7 shows the movement of the water body and the sphere at selected time instances. The sphere moves down vertically, generating axisymmetric splashes. At 0.01 s, the water below the sphere is pushed down, while the water around the sphere is squeezed and moves up to form the splashes. From 0.01 s to 0.03 s, the sphere keeps moving down. A cavity with a radius similar to that of the sphere is observed above the sphere. The cavity collapses after 0.03 s, resulting in an upward water jet. At 0.08 s, the flow patterns in the cases with sphere densities of 860 and 1140 kg/m³ are similar, having a funnel-shaped cavity above the sphere. For the case with the density of 2300 kg/m³, the sphere keeps dropping with a high velocity. The simulated flow pattern agrees well with the experiment in terms of the free surface, cavity and water jet. It is demonstrated that the resolved SPH-DEM coupling method can model the interaction between fluid and free floating bodies.

6.2. Non-Newtonian Poiseuille flow

In this section, a two-dimensional simulation of Poiseuille flow is performed to validate the SPH for non-Newtonian fluids and the SPH-DEM boundary treatment. In this case, the non-Newtonian fluid, driven by a constant acceleration a , flows in the x -direction. As show in Fig. 8, the problem domain is a flow confined between two walls with a distance of H . The periodic boundary condition is imposed at the two ends. The upper ($z = H$) and lower ($z = 0$) boundaries are represented by rigid DEM bodies. The non-Newtonian fluid is modelled using the

Fig. 6. Evolutions of the water entry depth from the experiments [118], CEL [119], and SPH-DEM.

Fig. 7. The process of water entry of the spheres with different densities.

Fig. 8. The configuration and boundary conditions of the non-Newtonian Poiseuille flow.

regularized Bingham model. As given in [120], the analytical solution for this problem is

$$v_x = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \frac{\rho a H^2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{1}{4} - \left(\frac{z}{H} - 1 \right)^2 \right) - \frac{\tau_0 z}{\mu_0} & \frac{1}{2} \geq \left| \frac{z}{H} - \frac{1}{2} \right| \geq z_0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \frac{\rho a H^2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{1}{2} - z_0 \right)^2 & z_0 \geq \left| \frac{z}{H} - \frac{1}{2} \right| \end{cases} \quad (45)$$

where v_x is the flow velocity in the x -direction. $z_0 = \tau_0/(\rho a H)$ is the position where the Bingham fluids reach the yield condition. For this problem, the key factor in numerical simulation is the correct enforcement of the non-slip boundary condition. In the numerical modelling, the two boundaries are modelled as DEM objects and discretized using contact nodes with the same spacing like the SPH particles. The non-slip solid boundary is modelled by calculating the interaction forces in normal and tangential directions as presented in Section 4. The parameters used in this test are listed in Table 1. Three different yield stress, i.e. 0.01, 0.02,

Table 1
Parameters used in the simulation of Poiseuille flow.

Particle spacing (m)	ρ (kg/m ³)	a (m/s ²)	H (m)	μ_0 (Pa·s)	τ_0 (Pa)
0.005	1000	0.001	0.1	0.1	0.01, 0.02, 0.03

and 0.03 Pa, are used in the simulation. An important non-dimensional number for Bingham flows is the Bingham number, defined in this case as $\tau_0 H / (2\mu_0 U_0)$, where U_0 is the velocity of the plug layer. In the three simulations, the corresponding Bingham numbers are 0.625, 2.222, and 7.500, respectively. The sound speed c_0 of the fluid at the reference density is taken as 30 m/s, which restricts the density variation well below 1%.

The time history of the maximum velocity in the three simulations with different yield stresses is given in Fig. 9. In the three simulations, the initial particle spacing is $\Delta x = 0.5$ cm. It can be seen that all the flows eventually reach the steady state. A fluid with lower yield stress needs more time to reach the steady state and has larger maximum velocity. To check the influence of the initial particle spacing, three simulations with $\Delta x = 0.25, 0.4,$ and 0.5 cm are carried out. The two wall boundaries, which are represented as DEM objects, are discretized using contact nodes with the same spacing as the SPH particles. The yield stress in the three simulations is $\tau_0 = 0.03$ Pa. The velocity between the two walls in the steady state is given in Fig. 10. It is found that there are no notable differences between the results from simulations with different initial spacing, indicating that for this case the particle spacing $\Delta x = 0.5$ cm is fine enough. Further refining the particle spacing does not result in a more accurate computation.

The velocity profiles obtained with the three yield stresses are given in Fig. 11. It can be seen that the simulations capture the important feature of the Bingham Poiseuille flows, i.e. there exists a plug layer in

Fig. 9. The change of maximum velocity in the three simulations with different yield stresses.

which the fluid is unyielded. The maximum velocities and the widths of the plug layers are reasonably reproduced in the three simulations. As the yield stress increases, the maximum velocity decreases and the unyielded plug zone becomes wider. However, some discrepancies between the numerical and analytical solutions can be observed near the boundaries, which indicates that the non-slip boundary is not imposed exactly. Although the renormalization scheme introduced in Section 4.3 is employed, it can be seen that the computation using a single pair of SPH particle and contact node is but an approximation of the contribution from the truncated support domain. Nevertheless, the proposed coupling method is simple and efficient, and can capture the salient behaviour on the interfaces between solids and non-Newtonian fluids. Therefore, it is employed in the SPH-DEM coupling framework to model heterogeneous suspensions.

6.3. Rock collapse

In the coupled SPH-DEM framework, the solid particles are modelled using SMR-DEM. In this section, the gravity-driven rock collapse is modelled to demonstrate the capability of SMR-DEM and study the

Fig. 10. Velocity profiles obtained from different numerical resolutions with $\tau_0 = 0.03$ Pa.

Fig. 11. Comparison of the velocity profile between numerical results (dots) and analytical solutions (lines).

influence of particle shape on the flow pattern of particle assemblies. In this case, four rock assemblies, composed of particles of four different shapes, i.e. sphere, ellipsoid, natural pebble, and tetrahedron, are modelled. The DEM models for natural pebbles are generated from ten actual pebbles using the ‘Structure-from-Motion’ photogrammetry strategy [121]. The images of the natural pebbles and the generated DEM particles are shown in Fig. 12. The three principal dimensions of the long axis (a_p), intermediate axis (b_p), and short axis (c_p) are calculated for the generated pebbles. Then two ratios, b_p/a_p and c_p/b_p can be defined. These two ratios of the ten pebbles are averaged, and the resulted ratios are used to define the ellipsoids.

Each rock assembly consists of 1350 particles of different shapes. The density of all particles is assumed to be 1700 kg/m^3 . The radius of the spherical particles is set as 1 cm. To make sure that the initial heights of the rock columns are the same, the particles of different shape are properly scaled. The mass of the particles ranges between 5.31 and 8.53 g. In the numerical simulation, the rock assemblies are filled in the right part of a container and are confined by a fixed gate, as shown in Fig. 13. For the ellipsoids, tetrahedrons and natural pebbles, each particle is initialized with a random orientation and released from a specific height. Especially, for the simulation with natural pebbles, each pebble is generated from a random model in the template shown in Fig. 12. The gate is removed when the packing reaches a stable state. Driven by gravity, the rock assemblies collapse and flow to the left part of the container. The parameters used in the simulation are listed in Table 2. The parameters are chosen somewhat freely in the common parameter ranges [27,50], because there lacks experimental data for calibration. For convenience, the contact parameters for particle-particle and particle-boundary are assumed to be identical. The numbers of contact nodes for one particle are 212, 212, 502, and 580 for sphere, ellipsoid, natural pebble and tetrahedron, respectively. The local average spacing for contact nodes on boundaries is around 0.5 cm. Fig. 13 shows the final packings of the four rock assemblies. The time step is determined based on Eq. (40d).

Fig. 14 shows the profiles of the rock assemblies when the systems reach a stable state after collapse. Particles are coloured by their displacement. It can be seen that although the same friction coefficient is employed, the maximum displacement of the rock assemblies decreases progressively as the particle angularity increases. For the collapse of spheres, ellipsoids and round pebbles, the free surface is approximately a flat line from bottom to top. On the other hand, an undisturbed flat top surface can be observed for the assembly of tetrahedral particles. The

Fig. 12. The rounded pebble models used in the simulation (upper: natural pebbles; lower: generated particles).

surfaces of the final deposits are extracted using Matlab's image processing toolbox. The slope of the flat free surfaces is then fitted using the least squares method, and the angle of repose is calculated based on the fitted straight line. Table 3 summarizes the results of angle of repose for different particle shapes. As expected, the angle of repose for

the spherical particles is the smallest, while that for the tetrahedral particles is the largest. This is because that the entanglements of angular particles prevents them from rolling down along the free surface. Moreover, the angle of repose for the natural pebbles is slightly larger than that for the ellipsoids. This is because that although the shape ratios of

Fig. 13. The final packing status of the granular column with four different particle shapes (unit: cm).

Table 2
Parameters used in the simulation of granular collapse.

Parameter	Value
Particle density (kg/m^3)	1700
Friction coefficient	0.65
Normal stiffness (N/m)	1.0×10^5
Tangential stiffness (N/m)	6.0×10^4
Restitution coefficient	0.1
Time step (s)	2.0×10^{-5}

these two kinds of particles are similar, the angularity for the pebbles is larger than that for the ellipsoids. According to the numerical results, the particle shape has a significant influence on the flow pattern of granular system. The angle of repose is not only dependent on the frictional coefficient, but also on the particle shape. The numerical case also demonstrates that the SMR-DEM with the unified hybrid contact method can reasonably simulate particle systems of complex and arbitrary irregular shapes. This observation is also well corroborated by our previous results in [50]. Nevertheless, future work will be focused on laboratory tests to have rigorous quantitative validation.

6.4. Gravity-driven fresh concrete flows

In this section, fresh concrete flows are studied numerically to check the capability of the coupled SPH-DEM method in modelling heterogeneous suspensions. The experiment carried out by Leonardi et al. [31] is considered as a benchmark for this simulation. In the laboratory test, the concrete flow consists of cement paste and 1000 silica pebbles. According to the rheometer test, a regularized Bingham model can be employed to model the rheological behaviour of the cement paste. This problem was also studied numerically using coupled LBM-DEM method [31], where the irregular particles are represented by combining four spheres to form a pyramid-like shape. In [37], the pebbles are simplified as spherical particles.

In this study, four different shapes are used to represent the granular phase, i.e. sphere, ellipsoid, natural pebble, and tetrahedron. The influence of particle shape on suspension flow is investigated. In the simulation, each particle has the same density and weight as that in the laboratory test. The 1000 particles have a total weight of 2.629 kg. The models of pebble used in this section is generated from the template given in Section 6.3 with proper scaling. Table 4 summarizes the parameters used in the simulation. For the solid phase, the contact parameters

Table 3
The results of angle of repose for different particle shapes.

Particle shape	Sphere	Ellipsoid	Pebble	Tetrahedron
Angle of repose ($^\circ$)	20.46	26.78	28.62	38.45

Table 4
Parameters used in the simulation of fresh concrete flows.

Solid	Fluid		
DEM particle number	1000	Initial particle spacing (m)	0.002
Density (kg/m^3)	2680	Density (kg/m^3)	1800
Friction coefficient	0.2	Plastic viscosity (Pa-s)	0.15
Normal stiffness (N/m)	1.0×10^5	Yield stress (Pa)	62.0
Tangential stiffness (N/m)	6.0×10^4	Time step (s)	1.0×10^{-5}
Restitution coefficient	0.1		

Fig. 15. The initial setup of the gravity-driven fresh concrete flow test with natural pebbles.

for the particle-particle and particle-boundary are assumed to be the same. The coefficients in the stabilization term Π_{ij} are: $\alpha_1 = 0.01$ and $\alpha_2 = 0.0$ for the artificial viscosity, and $b = 0.5$ for artificial pressure. These parameters are common choices in SPH simulations of Newtonian and non-Newtonian flows [24,67,71]. The sound speed c_0 in the fluid at the reference density is taken as 150 m/s, which is much larger than ten times of the expected maximum velocity in the flow.

The initial configuration of the problem is given in Fig. 15, where fresh concrete with natural pebbles is shown. The cement paste is modelled using SPH particles, whereas the rigid aggregates are

Fig. 14. The final profiles of the granular assemblies with different particle shapes.

Fig. 16. Snapshots of gravity-driven fresh concrete flow with spherical particles at different time.

represented by DEM particles, which are uniformly distributed in the fluid phase with random orientation. The mixture is filled in a cubic box with a side length of 15 cm. The cubic box is open on top and bottom and positioned over a plate inclined at 15°. The cubic box and inclined plate are represented using rigid DEM bodies, where the contact nodes have the same spacing as the initial particle spacing of the fluid particles. The test is performed by moving the box upwards with a speed of 0.15 m/s. The mixture will spread on the plate under the effect of gravity.

Fig. 16 shows four snapshots of the simulated gravity-driven free-surface flow with spherical particles at time instants of $t = 0.2, 0.4, 1.0$ and 3.0 s. The DEM particles are represented in light gray, and the fluid phase is coloured by the magnitude of velocity. With the lifting of the box, the fresh concrete spreads on the inclined plate and flows down under gravity. After around 0.4 s, the whole sample flows out of the box. The largest velocity can be found near the front of the flow. Due to the viscoplastic behaviour of the cement paste, the viscous and frictional effect of the boundary, and the fluid–solid interaction, the flow gradually slows down. The flow becomes very slow after 1 s. Because the regularized Bingham model is employed, the fluid becomes very viscous after 3 s and has only negligible motions. From a numerical viewpoint, it can be regarded that the flow stops and a quasi-equilibrium state is reached.

Figs. 17–19 illustrate the simulated flow processes of concretes with ellipsoids, natural pebbles, and tetrahedrons. Compared with the case with spherical particles, the outflow velocity of the suspension becomes slower as the particle angularity increases. In particular, for the case with tetrahedral particles, the flow velocity is much smaller, as it is found that at $t = 0.4$ s a large portion of the concrete is still in the box, whereas for the other three cases, all materials have flowed out of the box at that time instance. The runout and spread area of the concrete with tetrahedrons are also smaller than those in the other three cases. There are mainly two reasons for the smaller runout and deposition area. First, as discussed in Section 6.3, tetrahedral particles tend to form entanglement, which reduces the fluidity of the mixture. Second, tetrahedral particles have larger area in contact with the inclined plate, which further prevents the mixture from flowing.

The final deposition areas of the four concrete flows are shown in Fig. 20. First, the result obtained from the case with natural pebbles are compared with the experimental and LBM-DEM results [31] in Fig. 20(a). A good agreement between the three deposition shapes is observed. Because of the very similar final depositions and the lack of more experimental data, it is difficult to tell which method has higher accuracy. Nevertheless, in the present SPH-DEM method, techniques such as the boundary tracking used in [31] is not required, which gives rise to simpler formulations and more convenient implementation.

For the numerical results with different particle shapes, it can be seen that the final spread areas for the spherical and ellipsoidal particles are similar, which are slightly larger than the final area of natural pebbles. This is unsurprising, as the surface smoothness of the natural pebbles is lower than the spherical and ellipsoidal particles. Besides, the natural pebbles have higher angularity. The two factors combined result in a lower fluidity of the concrete with natural pebbles. The final deposition for the tetrahedral particles is much smaller than that for the other three shapes. In the concrete with tetrahedrons, there is also an obvious separation of the fluid and solid phases at the early stage of the flow, which is not observed in other cases. This phenomenon indicates that in this flow, in the early stage the two phases have very different fluidity. The results show that the particle shape has significant influence on the property of heterogeneous suspension. Moreover, it is found that the developed SPH-DEM method can correctly model the interaction between non-Newtonian fluids and solid particles of arbitrarily irregular shape, and may find applications in debris flow, drilling, concrete preparation and casting, among others.

The information of numerical efficiency of this test case is summarized in Table 5, where FPS (frames per second), defined as the number of computational steps executed in one second of wall-clock time, is used to measure the numerical efficiency. The simulations are performed using a laptop with a 'NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2070 Mobile' graphic card, which has 8 GB memory and 2560 CUDA cores. In the simulations with spherical and ellipsoid particles, the total number of SPH particle and contact node is almost the same. Although the particle shape is different, for these two simulations it is found that the FPS and total simulation time are almost the same. This finding indicates that the

Fig. 17. Snapshots of gravity-driven fresh concrete flow with ellipsoid particles at different time.

numerical efficiency of the coupled SPH-DEM method is independent of the particle shape. Instead, the numerical efficiency depends on the number of SPH particle and contact nodes. This conclusion can be confirmed by the cases with natural pebbles and tetrahedrons. In this two cases, more contact nodes are used to represent the DEM particles. As a consequence, the FPS decreases almost proportionally, leading to longer simulation time.

With the presented coupled SPH-DEM method, practical problems involving heterogeneous suspensions can be efficiently simulated

using simple laptops and desktops. However, for extremely large scale engineering problems, the simulation time may be too long; therefore, more efficient algorithms and advanced acceleration techniques are required. Consequently, one of the future research focuses is to implement more efficient multi-GPU acceleration. Furthermore, in the present SMR-DEM method, the node spacing is uniform for large and small DEM particles. This is inefficient if the size of DEM particles varies considerably. Therefore, it is needed to develop improved contact detection methods suitable for non-uniform node discretization.

Fig. 18. Snapshots of gravity-driven fresh concrete flow with natural pebbles at different time.

Fig. 19. Snapshots of gravity-driven fresh concrete flow with tetrahedral particles at different time.

Fig. 20. Final deposition area of the gravity-driven fresh concrete flows.

Table 5
Summary of numerical efficiency of fresh concrete flow.

Shape	SPH particle number	DEM particle number	Contact node number	FPS	Total time (hh:mm)
Sphere	240,771	1000	512,475	66.9	04:46
Ellipsoid	240,690	1000	512,475	67.0	04:44
Pebble	232,583	1000	790,850	45.2	06:51
Tetrahedron	218,200	1000	958,875	42.0	07:32

7. Summary

In this paper, a fully resolved coupled SPH-DEM method is developed for the simulation of heterogeneous suspensions with non-Newtonian fluids and arbitrarily shaped solid particles. The fluid phase

is modelled using weakly-compressible SPH with the regularized Bingham model, whereas the solid particles are modelled with the surface mesh represented DEM. Solid particles are represented using contact nodes obtained from triangular surface mesh. A unified hybrid contact method is proposed to handle SPH-boundary, SPH-DEM, DEM-DEM, and DEM-boundary interaction.

The main features of the coupling method proposed here are three-fold. First, the interaction force between the fluid and solid phases is divided into normal and tangential components. The normal force is computed based on the assumption of partial penetration, which avoids calculating the variables such as velocity, pressure and stresses for boundary particles. In the tangential direction, a viscous shear force is applied based on the discretization of shear stress gradient. As demonstrated in the simulation of Poiseuille flow, the viscous shear force can reproduce the non-slip boundary condition. Meanwhile, by neglecting the viscous force, a free-slip boundary condition can be modelled.

Moreover, the form of interaction force can be straightforwardly extended to contact problems of other materials, such as frictional soil-rigid body interaction. Second, the recently developed SMR-DEM [50] is used for solid phase modelling. SMR-DEM is highly versatile and can model arbitrarily shaped particles which makes it possible to take the particle shape into consideration in the simulation of fluid-solid interaction in free-surface flow. Moreover, the computational cost per particle depends on the number of contact nodes per particle, not on particle shapes. This feature makes it particularly suitable for problems with complex irregular shapes. Third, both SPH and DEM are suitable for parallel computing, because most computations take place independently at SPH particles or DEM contact nodes. Based on the unified hybrid contact method, all the interactions except SPH-SPH internal forces can be handled in a unified fashion. This allows straightforward GPU parallelization and efficient computation.

The coupling method are validated through several simulations, i.e., the water entry of spheres, the non-Newtonian Poiseuille flow, and the collapse of granular assemblies. The results show that the presented method captures the salient behaviours of: (1) particle assemblies with irregular shapes, (2) interaction between non-Newtonian fluid flows and fixed/moving objects. Furthermore, the presented method is employed to model fresh concrete flows with four different aggregate shapes. A good agreement between the experiments and the numerical results from the case with natural pebbles is obtained. By comparing the numerical results, it is found that the particle shape has a significant influence on the flow behaviour of heterogeneous suspensions. Future work will focus on: (1) improving numerical efficiency by multi-GPU acceleration and adaptive discretization, (2) quantitatively validating the SPH-DEM framework using laboratory tests, (3) applying the method to practical problems such as debris flows and concrete flows.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None.

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Appendix A. Derivation of the renormalized kernel gradient

Following the kernel gradient correction method in Chen et al. [105], the kernel gradient correction coefficient can be derived from the Taylor series expansion. Taking the one-dimension case for example, expand the Taylor series for $f(x)$ at x_i

$$f(x) = f(x_i) + \nabla f(x_i)(x-x_i) + \frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 f(x_i)(x-x_i)^2 + \dots \tag{A.1}$$

Neglecting the second and higher terms, multiplying both sides by $\nabla_i W(x-x_i)$, and integrating over the domain Ω , we have

$$\int_{\Omega} f(x)\nabla_i W(x-x_i)dx = \int_{\Omega} f(x_i)\nabla_i W(x-x_i)dx + \int_{\Omega} \nabla f(x_i)(x-x_i)\nabla_i W(x-x_i)dx \tag{A.2}$$

With SPH discretization, the summation form of Eq. (2) is written as

$$\sum_j f(x_j)\nabla_i W_{ij} \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} = \sum_j f(x_i)\nabla_i W_{ij} \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} + \sum_j \nabla f(x_i)(x_j-x_i)\nabla_i W_{ij} \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} \tag{A.3}$$

The corrective particle approximation for $\nabla f(x_i)$ can be written as

$$\nabla f(x_i) = \frac{\sum_j [f(x_j)-f(x_i)]\nabla_i W_{ij}m_j/\rho_j}{\sum_j (x_j-x_i)\nabla_i W_{ij}m_j/\rho_j} = \frac{1}{L_i} \sum_j [f(x_j)-f(x_i)]\nabla_i W_{ij} \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} \tag{A.4}$$

where L_i is the correction coefficient.

As shown in Fig. 2, there are only one contact node s in the support domain of fluid particle f . As a result, the correction coefficient L_f can be obtained

$$L_f = \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} (\mathbf{x}_s - \mathbf{x}_f) \cdot \nabla_f W_{fs}^1 \frac{m_s}{\rho_s} = (\mathbf{x}_s - \mathbf{x}_f) \cdot \nabla_f W_{fs}^1 \Delta x \tag{A.5}$$

where \mathbf{x}_s and \mathbf{x}_f are the positions of the contact node and fluid particle, respectively. m_s and ρ_s represent the mass and density of the contact node, which are taken the same as those of the fluid particle. Δx is the initial spacing of the SPH particles. The term Δx^2 is used to correct the 1D kernel gradient for 3D simulations.

Using the correction coefficient, the renormalized kernel gradient is defined as

$$\tilde{\nabla}_f W_{fs} = \frac{\xi}{\Delta x^2} \tilde{\nabla}_f W_{fs}^1 = \frac{\xi}{\Delta x^2} \frac{\nabla_f W_{fs}^1}{L_f} \tag{A.6}$$

The term Δx^2 is again used to correct the 1D kernel gradient. The coefficient ξ is the fraction of the truncated part of the support domain. It is used to correct the computed viscous force, because the forces from other SPH fluid particles are already considered. ξ can be calculated using the following form

$$\xi = \frac{\int_{x_{sf}}^{2h} x \nabla W^1(x) dx}{\int_{-2h}^{2h} x \nabla W^1(x) dx} = \frac{\int_0^{2h} x \nabla W^1(x) dx - \int_0^{x_{sf}} x \nabla W^1(x) dx}{\int_{-2h}^{2h} x \nabla W^1(x) dx} \tag{A.7}$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} - \int_0^{x_{sf}} x \nabla W^1(x) dx \approx \frac{1}{2} - \int_0^{\Delta x/2} x \nabla W^1(x) dx$$

where $x_{sf} = \|\mathbf{x}_s - \mathbf{x}_f\|$ is the distance between the contact node and the fluid particle, which is close to $\Delta x/2$ in a quasi-uniform particle distribution. Note that $\int_{-2h}^{2h} x \nabla W^1(x) dx = 1$ and $\int_0^{2h} x \nabla W^1(x) dx = 1/2$. The approximation of ξ is a constant dependent on the initial spacing, the smoothing length, and the kernel type. For the Wendland kernel, it can be computed at the beginning of the simulation as

$$\xi \approx \frac{1}{2} - \int_0^{\Delta x/2} x \nabla W^1(x) dx = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{15}{32h^3} \int_0^{\Delta x/2} x^2 \left(2 - \frac{x}{h}\right)^2 dx \tag{A.8}$$

$$= \frac{1}{1024} (3q_0^5 - 30q_0^4 + 80q_0^3)$$

where $q_0 = \Delta x/h$ represents the ratio between the initial spacing and the smoothing length, which is taken as 0.741 in this paper. Consequently, the value of ξ is 0.476.

The final expression of the viscous tangential force can be obtained by replacing the original kernel gradient $\nabla_f W_{fs}$ with the corrected kernel gradient $\tilde{\nabla}_f W_{fs}$.

Declaration on Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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